

THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF GREAT BRITAIN

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The British education system is famous for its traditional teaching methods and long history. Also, students from other countries are interested in UK universities and schools. Therefore, the UK is also famous for its international educational places. There are many types of schools in the UK. Although their names may be similar to those in our country, the teaching system and oversight are fundamentally different. There are state, private and religious schools in the UK. The state schools are free for all children. And in this country, many children go to the state schools. The second one is a private school. Parents have to pay if they want their children to study there. Also, they have their own teaching methods and it is not the same as state schools. However, Private schools in the UK help to maintain social inequality¹. Because only wealthy families children can study there. . The last one is religious schools. In this type of school, students focus on a specific religion while learning school subjects like maths, chemistry and others. The British education system emphasizes critical thinking, independent learning, and active participation, rather than simple memorization.² Because of this reason in the UK, students are active and can debate with each other without problems.

Education is divided 4 stages: Primary education, Secondary education, further education and higher education. Unlike other countries, children start primary education at 5 age and they learn simple things such as reading, writing and arithmetic. Secondary education includes children who are between 11 and 16 years old. This is of paramount importance for them because they have to pass the exam before graduation of this stage. This exam is called GCSE (general certificate of secondary) Further education helps students to enter universities. In this stage they prepare A-level- test Higher education starts with bachelor degree and unlike other countries it last 3 year and they study only a year for master degree.

Although higher education is shorter student can learn many things. Because higher education is intensive and focus on main subject. If we compare this with others, in other countries students have to learn more subjects .

There are some rules at school and all students must follow them. Firstly, all students have to wear uniform in order to maintain equality. In some schools, students wear traditional clothes, which shows respect for their history and culture. Boys usually wear a shirt and trousers, while girls wear a blazer, blouse, and skirt or trousers. Colour is chosen by schools themselves and all school uniform have their logo. Secondly, students are not allowed using their phone. Thirdly, children do not have to miss school without a valid reason. If they do this, parents will pay payment. Schools have merit and detention system. Marit system for good

¹ Francis Green and David Kynaston, Engines of Privilege: Britain's private school problem (London: Bloomsbury, 2019), page-45

² Colin Brock, education in the United Kingdom (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2015), page-142

students. And detention is for punishing bad behavior, and they have to stay at school until the evening as a punishment.

Schools holidays: the academic year lasts from early September to July. They have three main breaks - Christmas, Easter and summer. Students spend their many times at school. They stay there from 8:39 a.m until 3:30 p.m. they focus on not only subject but also can do sport and other activities according to their interests. After finishing further education British students take gap year before starting higher education. It can help them to do career, experience and etc. Another thing is Sandwich course. Even though this course continue 4 years, after 2 degree they can take a full-time job for a year then return university again. This third degree is called sandwich course. Fresher week is organized for new students at university or colleges. There might be tours, themed meet-ups, kayaking – depending on your uni or college’s location, there will be a heap of activities on offer during your first week or so to help make the transition fun and get you better acquainted with your new home.³ Moreover, they can take free pizza and have lectures to loose stress during study. Apprenticeship Programs: Apprenticeships combine traditional daytime education with workplace learning. Students spend about 80% of their time working and 20% studying at college or university. Tuition is covered by the employer and government, and apprentices receive a salary. ⁴Tutorial System: In many countries, students attend lectures with hundreds of peers. At prestigious UK universities like Oxford and Cambridge (Oxbridge), the tutorial system is central. it allows students to receive personalized guidance and actively engage in deep academic discussions. which helps them develop critical thinking and improve their academic performance. As a result, students become more confident and independent learners.

They are better prepared to solve complex problems on their own and succeed in their future careers. One or two times a week, groups of 1–3 students meet with a professor (tutor). Before the meeting, students complete in-depth research essays or complex problem sets. These sessions are discussion-based, not lectures, challenging students’ logic and ideas. This is essential for them to assimilate knowledge and students can enhance their practical skills with professor. The system encourages independent thinking, not just memorization. British university exams rarely include “Yes/No” or simple multiple-choice questions. Students are presented with complex scenarios and asked to critically evaluate them. Even in the UK if you want to higher well-paid job, you have to learn critical thinking. To achieve a First-Class degree (A), students must demonstrate original ideas, compare theories, identify weaknesses in arguments, and support conclusions with evidence. This prepares students for leadership and research, as they learn to solve problems with no ready-made answers. Exams in the UK: Before official exams (GCSE or A-Level), students take “mock” exams, which simulate real exams closely. Final exams are checked by Exam Boards, ensuring fairness. In August, students go to school to open their results. This day is highly emotional and famous in the UK. It also boosts students’ confidence and communication skills, as they receive results openly, without hiding. Postcode Lottery: Education quality often depends on where a student lives—this is called the “Postcode Lottery.” Catchment Areas: Most state schools accept students only from a designated area. Parents may pay 20–30% more for a house in a top-rated school area, linking

³ UCAS, Undergraduate courses: sandwich courses and fresher’s week explained, UCAS Official Website, 2024, ucas.com

⁴ Education and skills funding agency, apprenticeship.gov.uk, 2024.

academic success to residence. Similarities Between the UK and Uzbekistan Education Systems: 12-year system, facilitating easier admission to international universities. Cambridge Curriculum: Some Uzbek Presidential and Specialized schools implement the Cambridge Assessment International Education (CAIE) program. Students take IGCSE and A-Level exams, assessed according to UK standards. Critical thinking instead of memorization: The traditional Uzbek system relied heavily on memorization. The new national curriculum emphasizes problem-solving and practical application of knowledge, similar to the UK system.

If we pay attention the history of UK education, they have some challenges and they were not famous and developed. On that time, preparation of teachers for the elementary schools were called "normal schools," but they are now known as "training colleges." Their purpose is to prepare students to become "certificated teachers" for the elementary schools, by increasing their general knowledge and by giving them instruction in the principles and practice of teaching. A training college may be an independent institution, or a department of a university, or a department of a collegiate institution providing instruction in the arts and sciences.

Each college must have a governing body, which is responsible for the curriculum and for the discipline of the students, including the supervision of those who do not reside in the college buildings.⁵ Because of starting world war 1, the number of teachers diminished. So government created new rules that after the age 14, all children had to leave the school. Unfortunately this rules brought the poor education. Then UK understood that only education can help them to develop their country. Besides this, on that time, all colleges had their own teaching methods. It interrupted them to prepare young teachers. Because their methods were really differently from each other. Another thing is that, students were advised to study far places. Because in their view, if they stayed in their own place, they wouldn't learn new things. However financial problems were appeared. In developing the education system, the UK introduced new rules for teachers and students. They increased teachers' salaries and made school attendance compulsory for all students. In addition, all schools in the UK were required to follow standardized teaching methods. They also introduced formal exams and other educational reforms. Furthermore, attention was given to improving schools in both cities and rural areas. These changes helped develop and strengthen the UK education system.

In conclusion, the development of the education system in the UK has been the result of many historical reforms and continuous improvements over time. Since the introduction of early laws such as the 1870 Education Act, the government has worked to make education more accessible to all children. Later reforms, including the 1944 Education Act, ensured free secondary education for all students. As a result, education became more equal and widely available across the country. In addition, modern reforms such as the National Curriculum have standardized what students learn in schools.⁶ Furthermore, policies such as school inspections and accountability systems have improved the overall quality of education⁷. Overall, these reforms have transformed the UK education system into a modern and highly organized structure. Although some challenges still remain, the system continues to evolve and adapt to new social and economic demands. Education is now considered one of the most important

⁵ Pater Sandiford, *The training of teachers in England and Wales* (New York: Columbia University, 1910), page-65.

⁶ House of Commons Library, "Education: Historical statistics", UK Parliament Research Briefings, 2012,

⁷ Revision World, "Education Policy, Inspections and Accountability Systems", RevisionWorld.com, 2024, <https://revisionworld.com>,

tools for national development and social progress. Therefore, the UK education system stands as a strong example for other countries aiming to improve their own systems.

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